

01/04/2026

FHERITALE

Newsletter 03

Update from Project Co-ordination

ANTONIO ROSATO + FRANCESCA MORELLI

Since our last update to you in 2025, the FHERITALE project has produced several notable outputs, many of which have been communicated at in-person scientific meetings. As always, we welcome service providers and communities not yet represented in the FHERITALE service directory to reach out to us! We would also like to draw your attention to the upcoming FHERITALE stakeholder meeting in Brussels on May 26 2026. This will be a great opportunity for researchers and policymakers to come together and reflect on the success of FHERITALE so far, as well as future plans for the project.

THE FHERITALE CONSORTIUM MET AT A WORKSHOP IN BUCHAREST IN OCTOBER 2025, HOSTED BY THE METROFOOD-RO NODE

This newsletter:

UPDATE FROM FHERITALE COORDINATORS

PAGE 01

IN-PERSON AND ONLINE EVENTS

PAGE 02

FHERITALE GAP ANALYSIS AND WHAT'S NEXT

PAGE 03

Building the FHERITALE Community

Within the FHERITALE project, we place great importance on disseminating the most relevant and timely topics to the scientific community while fostering opportunities for the exchange of input and perspectives. At every stage, we aim to establish connections linking research infrastructures, stakeholders and scientific experts. The outcome is an array of diverse insights and the creation of integrated solutions and innovative approaches.

BUCHAREST WORKSHOP

On 23 October 2025, FHERITALE partners met at IBA Bucharest for a productive meeting, designed to contribute towards the project's efforts in gap identification and thematic clustering.

[You can find out more here.](#)

Key Outcomes:

- Cross-domain dialogue established
- Initial clustering criteria validated
- Strong stakeholder engagement

WEBINAR SERIES

Innovation Through Access: FHERITALE and the JRC Nanobiotechnology Laboratory

This webinar featured an update from Antonio Rosato on the FHERITALE project so far, as well as an in-depth presentation from Andrea Valesia of the JRC Nanobiotechnology laboratory.

The webinar recording is available online [here](#).

Untargeted approaches to marine pollutant monitoring

This webinar featured talks from Didier Stien and Carlos Cordeiro, and showcased how mass-spectrometry-based techniques can be used to identify marine pollutants and monitor their effects.

The webinar recording is available online [here](#).

Subscribe to our social media accounts to stay informed about upcoming webinars!

FHERITALE Gap Analysis and Technology Needs

Based on an online survey and additional input gathered during a co-creation workshop, the project has taken its first steps towards identifying priority research and service needs, assessing the readiness of existing technologies, and highlighting the gaps and barriers that limit their effective use within the domains of food, health, and the environment. The results are six key clusters which can act as integrated service solutions.

160+ Responses

ADDRESSING NEEDS WITH SERVICES

GAPS, BARRIERS AND DOMAINS

- ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING
- ANALYTICAL & CHARACTERISATION SERVICES
- TOXICOLOGY & EXPOSURE MODELLING
- BIOLOGICAL MODELS & IN-VITRO SYSTEMS
- DATA INTEROPERABILITY & DIGITAL TOOLS
- SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING & FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS

Survey → Gap Analysis → Clusters → Integrated Services

WHAT TO EXPECT NEXT?

Upcoming meetings

- On 26 May 2026, the FHERITALE project is inviting stakeholders to attend an in-person event in Brussels.
- We will be presenting a poster at MNP2026 in Birmingham, UK in July 2026.

Outputs

- You can download outputs from the dedicated FHERITALE workspace on ZENODO.

Find out more about FHERITALE via our [website](#), and keep up to date with news via our social media channels

@FHERITALE

FHERITALE

FHERITALE.EU